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Acoustically active antibubbles for ultrasound imaging and targeted drug delivery.

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In the current day and age, image guided and targeted drug delivery is becoming a necessity as it allowed a larger amount of therapeutic agent to be delivered to a precise location, allowing for tailored treatment to each and every patient, theoretically improving the treatment efficacy, whilst reducing systemic side effects. One of the most cost effective imaging modalities is ultrasound imaging. It is capable of deep tissue imaging in three dimensions in real time. In addition, it can be done bedside at any location, and has little to no known side effects. Sonoporation takes advantage of the behaviour of commercially available microbubbles, otherwise known as ultrasound contrast agents, under ultrasound sonication to form transient pores in cells, allowing for increased drug uptake. Pre-clinical and clinical trials have shown great promise. Nevertheless, in all instances, the therapeutic agent is delivered intravenously; hence there are still systemic side effects. Here we investigate the possibility of using drug-cored gas microbubbles (antibubbles) as an alternative to typical contrast agent. These antibubbles consist of a drug core, encapsulated air, encapsulated by a nano-particle stabilised shell. Our work here investigated the acoustic linear and non-linear behaviour of these antibubbles and compares them to commercial microbubbles. By adding the drug inside the bubble, we can theoretically force the drug into selected cells. Theoretical simulations were performed to evaluate the resonance frequency and radius time curves under sonication. Broadband acoustic attenuation measurements were performed to identify the resonant frequency and were compared to the size distribution. Ultra-high speed imaging was performed at high acoustic amplitudes to visualise the non-linear behaviour and to evaluate the gas content. The antibubbles were also imaged using a clinical scanner and several probes to evaluate the increase in contrast and non-linear acoustic backscatter. Our results showed that these antibubbles were acoustically active and highly non-linear, in a similar fashion to traditional contrast agents. These antibubbles may have potential as an ultrasound activated high-capacity drug carrier.